

Synthesis of New Anilidopyrimidinethione Derivatives

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Interaction of acetoacetanilide (Ia) or its hydroxy derivative (Ib) with aromatic or heterocyclic aldehydes gave the corresponding α , β -unsaturated ketones(II). The reaction of alcoholic solution of(II) with thiourea in a basic catalyst gave the corresponding pyrimidinethione derivatives(III). Fusion of (III) with amines, active methylene, and methyl compounds gave the corresponding condensation products IV, V and VI.

PYRIMIDINE derivatives play a vital role in many biological processes¹⁻³, and as synthetic drugs⁴. Many synthetic members are important as vulcanizing accelerator agents and photography stabilizers⁵.

Extensive efforts have been made to prepare new members of pyrimidinethiones⁶⁻⁸.

Anilido derivatives of such compounds were not mentioned before. In this work new anilidopyrimidinethione derivatives were prepared.

Experimental

The ir spectra were determined with a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer using the KBr Wafer technique. All melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of aceto-o-hydroxyacetanilide(Ib): To a preheated ethylacetate (40 ml, 1.5 mole) at 110°, o-aminophenol (25 gm, 1.0 mole) was added. The reaction mixture was warmed at 100-110° for 30-40 minutes, then allowed to cool, when colourless needles from (Ib) was separated. The product was filtered off, washed with few ml ether and crystallised from ethanol into colourless needles, m.p. 110°. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₁NO₃: C, 62.18; H, 5.70; N, 7.25. Found: C, 62.22; H, 5.60; N, 7.09.

Synthesis of anilido- α , β -unsaturated ketone derivatives(II): A mixture of equimolecular amounts (0.05 mol) from Ia^a/or b and the aldehyde was fused for 10-15 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled and digested with petroleum ether (60-80); the separated products (II) was filtered off, washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from methanol-petroleum ether mixture (1:4). The anilido- α , β -unsaturated ketones(II) are coloured compounds ranging from yellow to orange-red, readily soluble in alcohols, acetic acid, dioxane, moderately soluble in chloroform and carbontetrachloride, sparingly soluble in petroleum ether. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Synthesis of (3H)-4-aryl-5-anilido-6-methylpyrimidine-2-thione derivatives(III): A mixture of II (0.005 mol), thiourea (0.0075 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and potassium hydroxide (0.0075 mol) was refluxed for 10-12 hr. The separated products obtained after cooling and pouring on acidified ice-water (HCl), were filtered off, washed with water, and crystallised from aqueous methanol (1:3). The anilidopyrimidinethiones(III) are coloured compounds ranging from yellow to brown, soluble in alcohols, dioxane, carbontetrachloride, moderately soluble in chloroform, sparingly soluble in benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether. Yield, 60-75%. The results are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 1—2-ANILIDO (OR o-HYDROXYANILIDO)-4-ARYL (OR FURYL)-BUT-3-ENE-2-ONE

X, R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis			
			Calcd.		Found	
			N	Cl	N	Cl
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	110	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	5.28	—	5.20	—
(b) H, c-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	4.98	—	4.89	—
(c) H, p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	4.74	—	4.69	—
(d) H, p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	170	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ NCl	4.67	11.85	4.59	11.60
(e) H, C ₆ H ₅ -CH=CH-	120	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	4.81	—	4.75	—
(f) H, C ₆ H ₅ O-	90	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	5.49	—	5.40	—
(g) OH, C ₆ H ₅ -	100	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	4.98	—	4.89	—
(h) OH, o-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	190	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	4.71	—	4.63	—
(i) OH, o,p-(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₅ N	4.47	—	4.38	—
(j) OH, p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	120	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	4.50	—	4.39	—
(k) OH, p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	92	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N	4.44	11.25	4.30	11.15
(l) OH, C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	125	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	4.56	—	4.48	—

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

TABLE 2—(3H)4-ARYL-5-ANILIDE-6-METHYLPYRIMIDINE-2-THIONE DERIVATIVES III

X, R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis					
			Calcd.			Found		
			N	S	Cl	N	S	Cl
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	180	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	13.00	9.91	—	12.90	9.78	—
(b) H, <i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	140	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.39	9.44	—	12.18	9.33	—
(c) H, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	150	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.9	9.06	—	11.52	8.99	—
(d) H, <i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	235-40	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₂ OSCl	11.76	8.96	9.8	11.60	8.88	9.75
(e) H, C ₆ H ₅ -CH=CH-	145	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ OS	12.02	9.17	—	11.89	9.02	—
(f) H, C ₆ H ₅ O-	138	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.42	10.22	—	13.3	10.12	—
(g) OH, <i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	205	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.83	9.01	—	11.72	8.89	—
(h) OH, <i>o,p</i> -(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	>300	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.32	8.62	—	11.20	8.45	—
(i) OH, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	160	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.98	8.67	—	11.28	8.50	—
(j) OH, <i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	170	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	12.43	9.47	—	12.30	9.70	—
(k) OH, C ₆ H ₅ -CH=CH-	175	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.51	8.77	—	11.38	8.62	—

TABLE 3—REACTION PRODUCTS (IV) OBTAINED FROM (III) AND AMINES

X, R, R'	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis			
			Calcd.		Found	
			N	Cl	N	Cl
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, C ₆ H ₅ -	230	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	14.66	—	14.45	—
(b) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, <i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	250	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₄ O	14.14	—	14.05	—
(c) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	220	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	13.59	—	13.38	—
(d) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, <i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	280	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	13.46	8.41	13.31	8.20
(e) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, <i>p</i> -COOH-C ₆ H ₄ -	340	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	13.14	—	12.99	—
(f) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, 2-C ₆ H ₄ N	320	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	13.23	—	13.05	—
(g) H, C ₆ H ₅ -, 3-C ₆ H ₄ N	300	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O	13.23	—	13.05	—

TABLE 4—REACTION PRODUCTS (V) OBTAINED FROM (III) AND ACTIVE METHYLENES

X, R, R', R''	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis	
			Calcd.	Found
			N	N
(a) H, -C ₆ H ₅ -, -COCH ₃ -, -COOC ₂ H ₅ -	315	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	10.02	9.89
(b) H, -C ₆ H ₅ -, -COOC ₂ H ₅ -, -COOC ₂ H ₅ -	325	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅	9.35	9.17
(c) H, -C ₆ H ₅ -, -CN, COOC ₂ H ₅ -	290	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃	13.93	13.77

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis.

TABLE 5—REACTION PRODUCTS (VI) OBTAINED FROM (III) AND ACTIVE METHYL SALTS

X, R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis			
			Calcd.		Found	
			N	I	N	I
(a) H, C ₆ H ₅ -	315	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ N ₄ O ₂ I	9.52	21.6	9.40	21.52
(b) H, C ₆ H ₅ O-	240	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₄ O ₂ I	9.69	21.97	9.50	21.82
(c) H, <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	250	C ₃₁ H ₃₁ N ₄ O ₂ I	9.60	20.55	8.95	20.21
(d) H, <i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	235	C ₃₀ H ₂₉ N ₄ O ₂ I	9.27	21.03	9.21	20.98

Reactions of anilidopyrimidinethiones(III) with amines, active methylenes and active methyl salts: An equimolecular mixture of the anilidopyrimidinethione(III) and the amine or the active methylene or methyl compound was fused for 5 minutes. On cooling and diluting with methanol, yellow substances of (IV), (V) and (VI) respectively separated out which were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield, 70%. The compounds prepared are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5 respectively.

Biological screening for selected pyrimidinethione derivatives: The culture was normal nutrient agar (N.A.) medium¹⁰ supplemented with one

gram yeast/litre, the bacterial suspension was prepared by adding one ml of sterile distilled water to a 24 hr old culture of the test organism grown on N. A. Slant. One ml aliquots of bacterial suspension were added to Erlenmeyer flasks containing 150 ml of N. A. and the flasks were incubated for 24 hr. Petri dishes containing sterile modified N. A. were flooded with the bacterial suspension of the test organisms (2 plates for each organism). Two filter paper discs (one cm diameter) containing the selected compounds (IIIa, IVa, IVf, Vc and VIa) dissolved in ethyleneglycol (10 mg/L) were placed on each plate. The plates were incubated at 37° for 24 hr and the diameter of the inhibition

X = H(a), X = OH(b)

(VIa-d)

zone was measured. The experiments were repeated 3 times and the results obtained were averaged. The results are given in Table 6.

TABLE 6—BACTERIOLOGICAL SCREENING OF SELECTED ANILIDOPYRIMIDINE THIONES AND THEIR REACTION PRODUCTS WITH AMINES, ACTIVE METHYLENES AND METHYLQUATERNARY SALTS

Organism Used	III _a	IV _a	IV _t	V _o	VI _a
<i>Staphylococcus albus</i>	—	—	—	slight	slight
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	+	+	+	+	slight
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	—	—	—	slight	—
<i>Sarcina lutea</i>	—	—	—	—	—

Results and Discussion

The condensation reaction of aldehydes and acetoacetanilide (Ia) and or aceto-*o*-hydroxyacetanilide (Ib) gave the corresponding anilido- α,β -unsaturated ketone (II). Their ir spectra showed strong absorption bands at 1690 cm^{-1} (conjugated carbonyl groups), 1600 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond) and 3320 cm^{-1} (νNH).

Synthesis of anilidopyrimidinethione derivatives (III): Interaction of (II a/or b) with thiourea in presence of potassium hydroxide gave the corresponding anilidopyrimidinethione derivatives. Ir spectra^{1,2} of these compounds showed well defined

bands characterising the pyrimidinethione ring at 3350 cm^{-1} (νNH), 1600 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$), 1380 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$) and 1480 cm^{-1} ($\nu-\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{S}$).

Reaction of anilidopyrimidinethiones (III) with amines, active methylene and methylquaternary salts: Anilidopyrimidinethione (III) was condensed with amines and active methylene compounds by fusion and gave products IV and V respectively. Also, interaction of III with active methylquaternary salts e.g., quinaldine ethiodide either by fusion or reflux in ethanol as a solvent gave the corresponding monomethine cyanine dye (VI). The structure of these compounds IV, V and VI was established on the basis of elemental analysis and ir spectra which showed disappearance of absorption bands at 1380 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$), 1480 cm^{-1} ($\nu\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{S}$), indicated disruption of C=S group.

Bactericidal activity of these compounds were tested against some gram positive and gram negative bacteria and it was found that these compounds have a remarkable activity, against *Bacillus subtilis*.

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